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Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform

Md. Anowar Hossain

Professor Dr. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, a first PhD entrepreneur all over the world on 22 August 2023

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Keywords

Quality services for crime protection, crime analysis, peace of mankind, international platform

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Table 1, Services for Crime Protection, Crime Analysis in general

Specialized Review Service	Cost for Six Months (For one-time payment)
Crime Protection review & reporting for a specific government all over the world	80000USD
Compliance review & reporting for national & international violence, conflict & war	80000USD
Crime Protection review for government & non-government organization	80000USD
Crime analysis & reporting for specific crime for judge court, high court & supreme court of a country	80000USD
Specialized review/reporting for the case of death penalty/life imprisonment	80000USD

NB: An additional cost will be added for national & international travel & accommodation

Process for Review

A written application to Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain through e-mail: enr.anowar@yahoo.com

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